

Towards an all composite aircraft fuselage

M.J.L. van Tooren, M.N. van Beijnen, I.P.M. van Stijn
Structures and Materials Laboratory
Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
Delft University of Technology

Abstract

Composites are not yet introduced into the fuselage structure of large civil aircraft. The use of sandwich construction could facilitate this introduction. With the currently available materials sandwich structures can be realized which are reliable with respect to mechanical loads and which are resistant to environmental degradation. The combination of continuous fibre reinforced thermosets and thermoplastics can facilitate the production of these large sandwich fuselages. When prefabricated in-situ foamed panels are used, close fit joints can be obtained with filling thermoset joint strips which are weak at the time of jointing. Damage tolerance can be obtained with a combination of the soft skin principle and damage stoppers incorporated in the facings. Damage tolerance analysis can be done with the flat plate stress intensity approach. The curvature effect is shown to be small for large airplanes.

Introduction

Although composites have been introduced in primary structural parts of large civil aircraft the main primary components, i.e. the pressurized fuselage and wing box structure, are still made of aluminium. Reasons for that are manifold and include both technical and economical reasons. The evolutionary character of aircraft development creates only minor possibilities for the introduction of new materials and technologies. The organization and equipment available at the aircraft manufacturers is primarily metal based. Initial fuselage analysis shows that a sound structural lay-out for damage tolerant composite structures will be different from the one for metal structures. The techniques for damage tolerance analysis for this type of structure are still under development.

In this paper only some design aspects of composite fuselage design will be discussed. The feasibility of composite fuselages however was already proved for small aircraft in 1941 with the Langley Aviation plane and the feasibility of composite pressurized sandwich fuselages with the Starship of Beechcraft.

Fuselage structures

The attention is focussed on fuselage structures since the development of a composite sandwich fuselage is expected to result in a considerable part reduction, reduced manufacturing and maintenance costs and in the most effective weight saving. Additional benefits like better intrinsic thermal and acoustic insulation could result in supplementary weight savings.

Figure 1: Complexity of the fuselage expressed in relative number of parts

The complexity of a metal stiffened shell fuselage structure is illustrated in figure 1 [1]. It can be seen that the fuselage contains almost a third of the total parts of the aircraft. This is caused by the used design principle, which is the stiffened shell concept. The large number of frames, stiffeners and coupling elements makes the fuselage a highly labour and capital intensive product to manufacture.

Figure 2: Effectiveness of weight saving as function of the position of the weight saved

The effectiveness of saved kilograms structural weight as function of their position in the aircraft is shown in figure 2 [1]. From this figure it is clear that weight saving in the fuselage is more profitable than in the wing.

Composite sandwich fuselage structures

The current metal fuselages are generally riveted stiffened shell structures. The alternative, the bonded sandwich construction, is an effective way of creating bending stiff structures from a relative small number of parts. The designers of aircraft fuselages have always been attracted by sandwich construction, but unfortunately, from a durability and manufacturing standpoint, they never had the right materials available.

The bonded wooden sandwich structures from the forties were effective and performed equally well as the metal ones in structural effectiveness but their nature made them susceptible to degradation by fungi, water etcetera. Metal sandwich structures have also been produced but also with metals water ingress is a large problem. Furthermore the bending stiffness of metal facings during sandwich panel production creates the need for a high accuracy of the core thickness to prevent problems like disbonds and crushed cores.

Nowadays the right materials are available. There is a number of facing and core materials available which can cope with environmental effects, for example Nomex honeycomb. From the reported experience with the Beech Starship [2] it can be concluded that sandwich structures which are damaged and exposed to humidity do absorb water but they are able to confine this absorption to an area only slightly larger than the damaged zone. Since the material itself will not degrade due to contact with water, 'corrosion' like problems are not a major concern with composite sandwich structures. Of course the materials must have a proven resistance to paint strippers, solvents and hydraulic fluids.

To conclude, composites, both thermosets and thermoplastics, are more flexible in the manufacturing stage, therefore bonding is in general easier.

Design concepts

In principle a sandwich aircraft fuselage is a cylinder consisting of a limited number of curved shells. The cylinder has to be divided into several substructures for several

reasons. First an adjustment of dimensions to loads should be possible. Second producibility and reparability demand a limited panel size. In circumferential direction a division into crown, side and keel panels can be made. Of course a further division can be used depending on the size of the aircraft. For conventional configured airplanes the main division in the axial direction can be the aft and fore fuselage. For each of these parts a further division into different sections can be made. The number of sections will be larger for larger aircraft. With a structure like this it will be possible to fulfill all the stiffness and strength criteria for the undamaged structure.

An indication of the required Nomex core height in the different shells of a sandwich fuselage with carbon fibre reinforced facings for an aircraft with the size of an Airbus A320 can be found in figure 3.

If the structure is damaged there should be a damage stopping capability of the structure. In the stiffened shell structure this will be incorporated by choosing the right dimensions and pitches of the stiffening elements. For sandwich structures this damage stopping capability will have to be incorporated separately.

Figure 3: Core height in keel, side and crown panels as function of axial position

A possible way to do this would be the incorporation of damage stoppers in the facings of the sandwich shells. These damage stoppers are stiff strips of unidirectional material which are able to 'catch' damages. These damage stoppers can be laminated into the facings in a 'waffle' like pattern. The mesh width of this pattern depends on the damage resistance of the used facing material and the design stresses in these facings. The joints between the different shells can be designed to act as crack stopper for large damages due to events like uncontained engine failures. Some preliminary test results on this principle will be discussed later on together with some remarks on damage resistance and damage tolerance of composites.

Other items that have to be considered in the design are lightning protection, maintainability, inspectability and reparability. Also acoustical and thermal insulation can be made part of the structural design. The fact that a core material is used in sandwiches opens the possibility for combining these insulation requirements with structural requirements. For example if honeycomb core material is used the cells of this material can be filled with insulating material. The insulating capability of a 1/2" thick sandwich plate of this type is comparable to a 20" aluminium plate.

Manufacturing aspects

The best way to manufacture composite sandwich fuselages will depend on the choice of materials and especially on the type of resin and preform used. Also the size of the aircraft is of importance.

If 'conventional' fibre reinforced epoxies and Nomex honeycomb cores are used, the size of the aircraft will dictate the number of divisions. There is probably a practical limit to

co-curing. For the Starship it was possible to co-cure the complete fuselage and the complete wing, but for airplanes with the size of an A320 this will require extremely large moulds and autoclaves. Besides that the required reparability of major damages will demand the possibility of exchanging fuselage panels, this means that reliable out-of-autoclave bonding techniques for panel to panel joints have to be developed. This seems feasible considering the existing field repair techniques.

The combination of Nomex honeycomb with other facing materials like fibre reinforced PEEK or PEI will give more problems if the panel to panel joint strips are also made out of these reinforced thermoplastics. The welding techniques for these materials are not far enough developed yet to enable easy production.

Another solution would be to join the thermoplastic sandwich panels with thermoset panel-to-panel joints. During assembly you will then achieve the required flexibility to overcome minor dimensional mismatches between different shells.

Also ARALL and Glare can be used as facing material. But with these metal laminates the problems with tolerances will arise again, knowing that these materials have their full bending stiffness already during manufacturing of the panels.

The last option discussed in this paper deals with in-situ foamed sandwich panels [3]. This manufacturing method allows for creating in-situ foamed curved sandwich shells with the possibility of variations in core height over the panel. Curved panels have been made in our laboratory already [4] and further research on creating full circular sections out of these panels is being done.

These in-situ foamed panels can be joint with thermoset strips in the same way as discussed earlier.

Damage tolerance

Metals versus composites

For metal fuselage structures the damage tolerance philosophy is somewhat easier to formulate than for composites. The main damage source, fatigue, and the damage growth are predictable in a workable way. Especially the fact that the damage initiator and the damage propagator are the same makes the analysis feasible. In metal structures the damage initiator is a predictable repeating tensile stress, an internal load, and the propagator is a repeating tensile stress. The damage self will be a crack.

In composite fuselages the main damage initiator will in principle be an impacting object which can be regarded as an 'unexpected' external load. The damage can be a crack, a hole, a delamination, and is mostly a combination of these three. The propagator is a repeating load, here compressive loads will be dominant. The damage growth mechanism is depending on the damage type.

Damage resistance and tolerance of pressurized sandwich fuselages

The damage resistance to low energy impact of the sandwich shell is of course influenced by the choice of facing and core materials. An additional design parameter is the relative thickness of the facings. For the same total thickness of the facings the designer can choose to put more material in the outer facing than in the inner facing.

Although the stress level due to the pressurization loads will be the same the stresses induced during impact will be different, resulting in a different damage resistance.

Also the damage tolerance of the sandwich shell is influenced. Although the damage tolerance of the facing alone is unchanged, the damage tolerance of the whole sandwich structure can be decreased. For the case that only the outer facing is damaged, the same damage size will give a larger decrease in residual strength of the panel since a larger part of the total facing thickness is damaged.

The damage tolerance of a sandwich shell without damage stoppers can be influenced in several ways. Here only two of them will be discussed. These are the modulus of elasticity ratio of inner and outer facing material and the flatwise core stiffness. Here only loads due to the pressurization are considered.

In large civil aircraft the pressurization causes a severe loading of the fuselage shells. The differential pressure causes in-plane stresses in the facings of a sandwich pressure vessel. The fact that these stresses are caused by an out of plane load, the internal pressure, means that there is a possibility to manipulate the ratio between stresses in inner and outer facings not only by choosing different materials for inner and outer facing but also by choosing a core material with appropriate mechanical properties.

In principle the stress ratio can be influenced by two parameters the structural parameter α and the modulus of elasticity ratio β . In practice the design parameters are the modulus of elasticity ratio of the facings and the flatwise core stiffness. The relation between the ratio between the circumferential stresses in inner (2) and outer (1) facing, r , and the parameters α and β is given by:

$$r = \frac{\sigma_{f1}}{\sigma_{f2}} = \frac{\beta}{1 + \alpha}; \quad \alpha = \frac{E_1 t_c t_1}{E_c R^2}; \quad \beta = \frac{E_1}{E_2}$$

This relation is plotted in figure 4. By creating a difference in Young's modulus between the two facings, $\beta \neq 1$, the stresses in the outer facing, which is the most susceptible to damage, can be kept relatively low. In the case of an outer skin with a low modulus of elasticity, $\beta < 1$, the fuselage can be said to have a soft skin.

The other way to change the ratio between the stresses in the facings is to change the modulus of elasticity of the core. From figure 5 it becomes clear that creating a soft skin is not feasible. Only for a very low core stiffness the effect is noticeable. Therefore the only realistic design parameter is the stiffness ratio of the facings.

The damage tolerance of the sandwich fuselage shells can be improved with damage stoppers connected to the facings in a waffle-like pattern. The dimensions of the waffle must be chosen on the basis of their position within the fuselage, just like frame pitch and stiffener pitch varies with this position. To check if this principle will

Figure 4: Stress ratio between facings as function of the structural parameter α for several values of β

work in practice some initial tests have been performed on stiffened panels. These will be discussed later on in this paper. First the residual strength analysis of unstiffened panels with holes and the residual strength analysis of panels with damage stoppers will be discussed briefly.

Residual strength analysis

The fact that the damage source for composite structures is external and not internal creates additional problems with the proof of structure. Not only the loads on the aircraft have to be simulated but also the damage has to be simulated since it is not created by the repeated loading. Since the main source of damage is impact this means that locations, energy levels and representative impactor geometries have to be defined, based on the characteristics of real impacting objects like hail, runway debris etc.

Since the mechanics behind damage formation and growth are in an early stage of development compliance with the airworthiness requirements can only be shown with tests, this is the same with metal structures.

To minimize premature failure in these tests it is however necessary to develop reliable prediction methods for residual strength analysis. In this paper a first attempt is made to predict residual strength of panels with cracks and holes and panels with damage stoppers and cracks. The cracks can be regarded as a worst case of impact damage.

Panels with holes and cracks

To describe the severity of the presence of a crack on the residual strength of a plate the stress intensity approach will be used here. For simplicity reasons only mode I cracks will be considered. The relation between residual strength, σ_{res} , and the half crack length, a , is given by the well known formula:

$$K_{Ic} = C\sigma_{res} \sqrt{\pi a}$$

The stress at which failure will occur for a certain crack length is dictated by the material property K_{Ic} . Although this is a scalar for isotropic materials, it is not for composite materials. The value of this fracture toughness will be a function of the angle between the crack and the material principal axes system. In this paper this will not be discussed any further. The crack will be thought to be parallel to the aircraft longitudinal axis and the material considered will be orthotropic with one of its principal material axis parallel to the crack. The influence of the plate not being infinite and other deviations from the infinite plate with a single crack are put in the geometry factor C. In this case C will be used to account for the presence of holes. This case can be thought of as a crack, simulating an impact damage, between two windows. The C-values for some positions of a crack of 25mm between two window holes with dimensions 130x175mm, in a representative carbon facing, are given in table I. They are calculated by solving the partial differential equation describing the stress field

Figure 5: Effect of core stiffness on stress ratio between facings

in an orthotropic plate with a row of three elliptical holes which are not necessarily equally shaped. The middle hole has its vertical axis set equal to zero thereby simulating a crack. The solution is a summation of three complex series for which the coefficients are determined by the boundary conditions [5]. The effect of the presence of the windows on the stress intensity factor is in all cases noticeable, but increases quickly when the crack is close to the window cut outs.

pos	C
250	1.59
230	1.75
210	2.00
190	2.44
170	3.62

Panels with damage stoppers and a crack

The effect of a damage stopper is best explained with a residual strength diagram (fig.6) In this diagram the residual strength of the facing and the damage stopper are plotted versus the crack length. In figure 6 this is done for a test panel of a representative fuselage skin composite with unidirectional carbon stiffeners. From the diagram it can be concluded that the damage stoppers have a considerable influence on the residual strength of the skin and that damage stopping ability can be brought into the structure in this way. The diagrams are calculated with the program CRACKS [6].

Table I Geometry factor as function of damage position

The calculations have been supported by test evidence, the tests showed even better crack stopping ability than expected from these diagrams.

Influence of curvature

All the previous discussions are based on flat plate analysis. Of course the real fuselage shell will be curved. The effect of this on stress concentration and intensity factors is not easy to calculate. For isotropic monolithic materials the effect is known [7]. This is shown in figure 8 [8] for a cylinder loaded with internal pressure. The stress concentration as function of ϕ , figure 7, is given for several values of the curvature parameter μ . This μ is defined by:

$$\mu = \frac{\sqrt[4]{12(1-\nu^2)}}{2} \frac{a}{\sqrt{Rt}}$$

The formulae for sandwich shells with isotropic facings, based on the same principles, have been developed [8] to judge the effect of the curvature on sandwich shells loaded with axial loads and internal pressure. Some results are shown in figure 9. From these figures it can be concluded that for shells with a radius equal to that of the A320 ($R=2000\text{mm}$) and a core height, $t_c > 12$

Figure 6: Residual strength diagram of CRFP panel with damage stoppers

Figure 7: Definition of cylinder geometry

the effect of curvature becomes small enough to be neglected. The effect is related to the sandwich curvature parameter, μ_s , defined by:

$$\mu_s = \frac{\sqrt[4]{12(1-\nu^2)}}{2} \frac{a}{R \sqrt{\frac{d^3}{t}}}$$

$$d = \sqrt[3]{\left[t_f^2 + 3(t_c + t_f)^2 \right] t}; \quad t = t_c + 2t_f;$$

Conclusions

The development of damage tolerant composite sandwich fuselages for large civil aircraft seems to be feasible. With the currently available materials and the proposed structural concepts it is possible to manufacture fuselage structures from a limited number of parts. The structure can be made damage tolerant by a well chosen combination of materials and structural methods like the proposed damage stoppers. The resulting structure will be maintainable and repairable. To come to a reliable damage tolerance analysis of composite sandwich fuselages the described analytical methods are just a first step. The methods have to be improved and further tests have to be performed.

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Figure 8: Stress distribution around a circular hole in a monolithic cylinder

Figure 9: Stress distribution around a circular hole in a sandwich cylinder.